

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:

Impacts on Climate and the Earth System

Freshwater and iceberg flux impacts with BISICLES-NEMO

Deliverable D6.1

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Cover sheet: Left: freshwater fluxes into the ocean due to iceberg melting, averaged over a 750-year UK Earth System Model control simulation with pre-industrial CO₂ concentrations; Right: 50-year mean anomaly in the iceberg meltwater fluxes centred on Year 100 of an idealised +8GtC/year CO₂ ramp-up experiment, a time period marked by an average global-mean 2°C surface air warming anomaly. In this anomaly plot, blue shading indicates additional freshwater entering the ocean, and red shading indicates a reduction in the freshwater flux.

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1. Publishable summary

Icebergs calve off the Antarctic Ice Sheet and melt in the Southern Ocean. The freshwater they deposit in the ocean can have an important influence on the density structure of the ocean and, hence, the circulation of globally important water masses. This deliverable explores how changes in the rate of melting of icebergs under increased atmospheric CO₂ concentration are projected onto different Southern Ocean density layers that outcrop around Antarctica. In addition, we consider the extreme case of a hypothetical Ross Ice Shelf collapse triggering the calving of a large number of icebergs around Antarctica over a short period. It is important to explore the impact of iceberg meltwater on density space because transport in the interior ocean occurs mostly along density layers. Outcropping density layers connect the surface Southern Ocean to the abyss and to the overturning circulation. The outcropping and the volume of water in the densest layers change in response to greenhouse gas-induced warming. This analysis is conducted using a coupled configuration of the UK Earth System Model (UKESM), whose ocean domain is represented by the NEMO model (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean; Madec and the NEMO System Team, 2024; Marsh et al., 2015; Merino et al., 2016). The ocean domain is coupled to a Unified Model (UM) atmosphere and a BISICLES ice sheet model.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

We analyse output from experiments with the coupled UK Earth System Model (UKESM) conducted under the TerraFIRMA protocol (Smith et al., 2025, preprint). The UKESM includes a NEMO (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean; Madec and the NEMO System Team, 2024; Marsh et al., 2015; Merino et al., 2016) ocean domain, a UK Met Office Unified Model (UM) representation of the atmosphere, and a BISICLES icesheet model, so NEMO–BISICLES forms the coupled ocean-ice sheet system that is of relevance to this deliverable.

The TerraFIRMA protocol prescribes the setup of an ensemble of simulations: a multi-centennial control simulation with preindustrial CO₂ concentrations; an idealised +8GtC/year CO₂ emissions ramp-up simulation branched from the control run; and a range of CO₂ emissions stabilisation or ramp-down scenarios branched from the ramp-up. In addition, a modification to the model boundary conditions allows us to impose a simulated ice shelf collapse in UKESM, so that the entire volume of a given ice shelf is suddenly converted into calved icebergs.

These sets of idealised simulations give us the opportunity to explore where anomalous iceberg meltwater goes – geographically and in terms of ocean density layers – under greenhouse-gas-induced warming. Furthermore, we explore the nonlocal climate impacts of anomalous iceberg calving, transport, and melting.

2.1.1 The fate of iceberg meltwater in density space under idealised greenhouse gas warming

In the fully coupled UKESM, the BISICLES ice sheet model calves icebergs that then enter the NEMO ocean domain as Lagrangian particles (Marsh et al., 2015; Merino et al., 2016). In a control simulation with preindustrial greenhouse gas concentrations, icebergs are commonly seen around Antarctica and

downstream of the Antarctic Peninsula along the so-called Antarctic Iceberg Alley. The pattern of iceberg motion is matched by a corresponding fingerprint in their surface meltwater contribution (Figure 1, left). This clearly shows that iceberg melting exhibits a distinct pattern, with high meltwater input along the Antarctic coast and a particularly high melting hotspot to the north-east of the Antarctic Peninsula. To capture these features, it is necessary to use an advanced iceberg model formulation that accounts for the details of iceberg drift (under wind forcing, ocean currents, and other terms) and the size distribution and melting of icebergs, see OCEAN ICE deliverable D2.1 and milestone MS12 ⁽¹⁾. Once the model accurately captures these features, we can use it to examine what happens under global warming scenarios.

Fig. 1: Left: freshwater fluxes into the ocean due to iceberg melting, averaged over a 750-year UK Earth System Model control simulation with pre-industrial CO_2 concentrations; Right: 50-year mean anomaly in the iceberg meltwater fluxes centred on Year 100 of an idealised +8GtC/year CO_2 ramp-up experiment, a time period marked by an average global-mean 2°C surface air warming anomaly. In this anomaly plot, blue shading indicates additional freshwater entering the ocean, and red indicates a reduction in the freshwater flux.

We first consider a UKESM ‘ramp-up’ simulation. The UKESM is an Earth System Model, meaning it includes the major components of the global carbon cycle, including atmospheric chemistry, ocean biogeochemistry, and a land surface scheme. As a result, it can be driven in ‘emissions mode’, where human emissions of greenhouse gases are prescribed, and the atmospheric concentration of greenhouse gases is part of the model solution alongside the resulting climate warming and other impacts (Smith et al., submitted). Another aspect of the UKESM is that it includes active ice sheets (Smith et al., 2022; Siahann et al., 2023), so that the evolution of the Antarctic Ice Sheet and its iceberg calving are also part of the solution. This capability is very unusual in a coupled climate model.

We first consider an idealised ‘ramp-up’ experiment. The simulations start from a long ‘control’ run with pre-industrial CO_2 emissions, which reaches a steady-state climate with the ice sheet held fixed. After several centuries, the calving and melting of icebergs are in a steady state, resulting in a steady average map of iceberg freshwater fluxes into the Southern Ocean (Figure 1, left). Then the ‘ramp-up’ experiment is commenced, in which steady 8 GtC/year anthropogenic CO_2 emissions are imposed, and the ice sheet is also

¹ D2.1 Modelling icebergs, bathymetry and sea ice interactions and Milestone 12 “D2.1 and D4.1 results added into BISICLES- NEMO”, available on Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/communities/oceanice/>

permitted to evolve. Under constant excess emissions, the atmospheric CO₂ concentration ‘ramps up’, the world warms, and so does the Southern Ocean. At the same time, we see acceleration and retreat of the Antarctic glaciers, and a strong freshening of the Southern Ocean. A full analysis of the polar climatic changes in these ‘ramp up’ experiments is presented in Smith et al. (submitted). The aspect considered in this part of OCEAN ICE is the evolution of the iceberg freshwater flux under this ‘ramping up’ climate change.

In response to this warming, we see more icebergs melting near the Antarctic coast and shelves and fewer icebergs travelling farther down the Antarctic Iceberg Alley (Figure 1, right). This effect is clearly visible a century into the greenhouse ramp-up simulation (Figure 1, right), when the global surface-air temperature anomaly reaches 2°C above pre-industrial conditions. Thus, this is the UKESM projection of iceberg changes under climatic conditions consistent with the Paris Climate Agreement. The changes are quite profound. Despite more icebergs calving from the Antarctic Ice Sheet, the warmer ocean and atmosphere conditions mean that these icebergs melt closer to the coast, leading to an increased freshwater input over the continental shelf seas surrounding Antarctica, and a ‘starvation’ of freshwater input further north.

Over the course of the whole 4-century-long CO₂ ramp-up experiment, we see a greatly exacerbated version of the same trend, with strongly increased iceberg melting in a very narrow band right next to the coast, and a negative melt rate anomaly over a much wider region offshore (Figure 2). The reason the pattern has become so extreme is that this simulation has experienced nearly 8 degrees of warming in global surface air temperature after this period, amplified to approximately 10 degrees of atmospheric warming over the Antarctic region (Smith et al, submitted). The reason the ramp-up experiment is so extreme is that it is continued past several global warming levels of interest, from which further stabilisation and ramp-down experiments are performed.

The focus of our work is the impact of these trends in iceberg melting on the global ocean, which means we must consider how they affect the water masses formed in the Southern Ocean. The iceberg-melting trend is particularly significant during the Southern Hemisphere winter months, when deep, dense water layers outcrop around Antarctica. The densest layers outcrop closest to the continent, while the lightest ones lie farther north. Thus, one may naively expect to see a trend towards more iceberg-induced freshening in the densest layers under global warming, since the change in iceberg freshwater input is greatest near the coast (Figures 1 and 2). However, this is not the case.

Fig. 2: Trends in the wintertime iceberg meltwater flux anomaly over the full course of the ramp-up simulation. Blue shading indicates more iceberg melting, and red shading indicates less melting.

As the planet warms in these ramp-up simulations, the UKESM predicts a freshening of the Southern Ocean, leading to a southward shift in the density surfaces. As a result, the waters closer to Antarctica are getting lighter. This means that the increased iceberg meltwater fluxes close to Antarctica are no longer being input into the densest water masses, but instead are being input into lighter water masses, which used to sit further north before climate change happened. In other words, the change in the surface density pattern overcompensates the geographical trend in changing iceberg melting, and the densest layers receive an overall reduced supply of iceberg meltwater in a warmer world.

This change is illustrated in Figure 3, which shows the trend in iceberg freshwater fluxes into the ocean during the ramp-up simulation for each density class in the surface ocean. This plot is calculated by matching the trends in patterns of iceberg freshwater input and surface density. The figure shows that the very lightest water masses (on the left side of the plot) show no trend in iceberg input because they are too far north. The next densest water masses, centred on $\sim 26 \text{ kg/m}^3$, have a gain in iceberg meltwater input during the ramp-up simulation. This is because these lighter water masses are shifted southward due to climate change and therefore receive increased freshwater input from icebergs near the coast (Figures 1 and 2). Finally, the densest water masses, centred on $\sim 28 \text{ kg/m}^3$, exhibit a decrease in iceberg freshwater input. This occurs because these densest waters are no longer being created by the Southern Ocean in the latter stages of the ramp-up simulation.

Fig. 3: Trends in the surface iceberg meltwater flux anomaly over the course of the ramp-up simulation in density space. The horizontal axis denotes the σ_3 potential density, the density anomaly that surface water would have if it were brought to a depth of 3 km in the ocean. Positive values on the y-axis indicate an increased supply of freshwater from icebergs into water of that density, while negative values indicate that less freshwater is being injected into that density class.

This single ramp-up experiment is actually part of a much larger ensemble of UKESM simulations, including several ramp-up simulations, stabilisation experiments branching at several different global warming levels, and ramp-down experiments branching from these stabilisation experiments (Smith et al, submitted). The intention of these stabilisation and ramp-down experiments is to examine the reversibility of climate changes if humans were to remove greenhouse gases from the atmosphere. This allows us to assess the potential long-term impacts of ‘overshooting’ climate change targets, such as those set by the Paris Climate Agreement. Smith et al. (submitted) find that in the UKESM, most aspects of Southern Hemisphere climate change are not simply reversible, meaning that the changes feature significant lags of many centuries in responding to the removal of greenhouse gases from the atmosphere. Here, we focus on the reversibility of deep-ocean water-mass changes in these ramp-down scenarios, arising from both changes in iceberg freshwater flux and other shifts in the Southern Ocean climate system.

Figure 4 shows the variability and trends in the volume of the dense Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW) in neutral density coordinates, in response to the ramp-up, stabilisation, and ramp-down in CO₂ concentrations. This reveals the system’s inertia in AABW trends and indicates a potential irreversible tipping point in AABW volume. The simulation starts in the top-middle section of this plot, under pre-industrial conditions, with a CO₂ concentration of approximately 300 ppmv and a high volume of dense AABW. Greenhouse gas emissions shift the system state to the right on this plot, and as CO₂ concentration increases, the AABW volume decreases because global warming reduces sea-ice production over the Antarctic continental shelf seas, where the densest AABW is produced.

In the simulation plotted, CO₂ emissions are ceased at ~ 450 ppmv, which corresponds to approximately 2 degrees C of global warming (Smith et al., submitted). However, the volume of AABW does not stabilise at this point and keeps declining. This is clear evidence of a strong lag in the climate system, by which

greenhouse gas emissions create long-lasting impacts that require many decades or even centuries to manifest. These long lags need to be accounted for when considering emissions policy.

After this stabilisation period, negative greenhouse gas emissions are applied to the simulation, causing the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere to decline - the trace moves to the left in the system diagram (Figure 4). However, there is no appreciable reversal in the decline of AABW for most of this period. It is only once the CO₂ concentration is reduced far below pre-industrial levels that the AABW volume starts to recover. This is clear evidence of hysteresis in the system, by which the AABW volume at any given moment is a function of the historical evolution of that quantity. This has a practical implication of huge importance. If we allow greenhouse gas emissions to reduce AABW quantities, as is occurring in the real world, it is much harder to reverse that change than it is to induce it in the first place.

Fig. 4: Simulated evolution of the volume of dense Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW) south of 60°S in response to a ramp-up and a ramp-down of atmospheric CO₂. The system starts with an initial AABW volume greater than 3×10^{16} m³, which decreases as the CO₂ concentration is ramped up, but does not immediately recover when the concentration is ramped down.

The initial results described in the above section will now be expanded and worked up into a paper, submitted before the end of the OCEAN ICE project.

2.1.2 Potential nonlocal impact of a Ross Ice Shelf collapse and iceberg calving

As well as employing the UKESM model in these general scenarios, in which all aspects of climate change are considered simultaneously, we can also use it for idealised experiments that isolate the influence of an individual climatic event. Here, we use the UKESM to perform an extreme-case simulation of an abrupt total collapse of the Ross Ice Shelf, such that its entire volume is converted into calved icebergs. This is of interest because our UKESM climate forecasts produce a very strong thinning of the Ross Ice Shelf over the 21st century (Siahaan et al. 2022), to the extent that, in reality, it would be expected to collapse. We hypothesise that this would introduce a sudden, large freshwater input into the Southern Ocean, which may have global consequences. Here, we conduct an idealised preliminary experiment into the influence of such a collapse.

In this experiment, we instantaneously remove the Ross Ice Shelf and then track the advection of the resulting icebergs as Lagrangian particles (Marsh et al., 2015; Merino et al., 2016) in the NEMO ocean domain of the UKESM. As these icebergs melt within and away from the Ross Sea, they suddenly freshen and stratify the Southern Ocean. This isolates the sea surface from warmer waters at depth, allowing the surface ocean to cool rapidly under the influence of the harsh Antarctic winter atmosphere. This induces a rapid increase in sea-ice cover, which further insulates the atmosphere from the ocean heat store. Overall, this leads to a widespread and substantial cooling around the Antarctic Ice Sheet (Figure 5). In addition, atmospheric teleconnections communicate the cooling signal beyond the Southern Ocean. This illustrates the potential for a nonlocal impact of the melting icebergs calved under a hypothetical Ross Ice Shelf collapse.

Fig. 5: Surface air temperature anomaly 4 years after a collapse of the Ross Ice Shelf computed relative to the unperturbed preindustrial control state.

There are several aspects of this climate response that require further investigation, such as the lack of cooling over the Weddell Sea region (bottom right region of Figure 5) and the teleconnection that appears to create regions of Arctic cooling (top of Figure 5) in response to this localised Antarctic perturbation (located in the bottom centre of Figure 5). These aspects will be further investigated.

2.2 References

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3. Results

Following the explanations in section 2, the main results can be summarised as follows:

- Our research provides insight into the changing spatial pattern of Antarctic iceberg distribution and melting under global warming.
- Our work identifies long-term depletion of the deep dense water masses around Antarctica under climate change and the potential that these changes may not be easily reversible.
- Our computer simulations highlight the widespread climatic impact of icebergs released during a catastrophic collapse of Antarctic ice shelves.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the following objectives of the project, as described in the Description of the Action.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica, particularly relating to ice sheet-ocean interaction and deep water formation and export.

This will assess the oceanic controls on heat and freshwater delivery to and from ‘cold’ (e.g. Weddell Sea) as well as ‘warm’ (Amundsen Sea) sites of ice sheet-ocean interaction around Antarctica, and the processes that control mixing, water mass formation and export over the continental shelves and subpolar basins.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by focusing on the impact of melting icebergs on the dense water formation sites in shelf seas. Our work gives a new perspective on the freshwater delivery from ‘cold’ and ‘warm’ cavities, as it considers a third option: a shelf sea like the Ross Sea, which hypothetically switches from a ‘cold’ to a ‘warm’ regime in the run-up to a hypothetical ice shelf collapse. Thus, our analysis provides unique and valuable insight into the impact of iceberg meltwater from cavities that transition to a warm regime.

O4: Quantify AIS melt sensitivity to climate forcing and reduce the ‘deep uncertainty’ in freshwater flux and SLR projections to 2300.

By combining newly developed coupled ice sheet-ocean models with innovative quantification of uncertainty and improved initialisation setups. This will produce projections of contributions from basal meltwater, iceberg calving, and surface runoff across a range of future climate scenarios, including those that may involve tipping points.

This deliverable contributes to this objective by examining the spatial and density patterns of iceberg meltwater under an idealised global-warming scenario and an ice-shelf collapse scenario. Although the results are based on extreme hypothetical scenarios, they still provide a qualitative assessment of the main factors governing the spatial pattern of iceberg meltwater distribution and its nonlocal impact.

O5: Assess how global ocean circulation is impacted by freshwater discharge from the northern and southern ice sheets.

Map the pathways and variability of Antarctic Bottom Water as it spreads north. Assess how this and other freshwater inputs modify climatically relevant ocean features, such as North Atlantic Deep Water formation, the deep overturning circulation, the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC), and the AMOC, up to millennial timescales.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by exploring the spatial and temporal trends and variability in the dense Antarctic Bottom Water under an idealised CO₂ ramp-up simulation. A set of additional idealised stabilisation and ramp-down simulations then allows us to assess the system’s inertia in the AABW trends and to highlight indicators that trends may have a degree of irreversibility.